

Electrochemical detection of DNA based on its interaction with safranin T

Wei Sun*, Jia-yu You and Kui Jiao

College of Chemistry and Molecular Engineering, Qingdao University of Science and Technology,
Qingdao 266042, People's Republic of China

E-mail : sunwei_1975@public.qd.sd.cn

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Abstract : A second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric method was established for the determination of microamount of DNA based on its interaction with safranin T (ST). In pH 6.0 Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution ST had a sensitive second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric reductive peak at -0.43 V (vs SCE). The addition of DNA into ST solution resulted in the decrease of peak current and negative movement of peak potential, which were the typical characteristics of electrostatic attraction of small molecule with DNA. The conditions of the binding reaction and the electrochemical detection were carefully studied. The influences of coexisting substances and ionic strength on the interaction were investigated. Under the selected conditions, the decrease of peak current was linear with DNA concentration in the range of $1.0 \sim 12.0$ mg/L with the linear regression equation as $\Delta I_p''(nA) = 58.96C (\mu\text{g/mL}) - 48.63$ ($n = 9$, $\gamma = 0.993$) and the detection limit as $0.79 \mu\text{g/mL}$ (3σ). Four synthetic samples were determined with satisfactory results and the recovery was in the range of 96.7 to 106.7% . The stoichiometry of the complex was calculated by the voltammetric method with the binding ratio as $1 : 2$ and the binding constant as 1.0×10^7 .

Keywords : Safranin T, DNA, linear sweep voltammetry, binding reaction, electrochemistry.

DNA is an important biomolecule and the quantitation of DNA is of great importance in life science and bioanalytical chemistry. Many methods have been proposed for the direct or indirect determination of DNA. The direct ultraviolet spectrophotometric absorption of DNA at 260 nm or the direct electrochemistry of DNA on mercury or other working electrodes such as carbon, gold, silver, carbon nanotube modified electrode, etc. had been widely investigated¹⁻³. Guanine and adenine of DNA had direct redox response on mercury electrode, but it suffered from less sensitivity⁴. Indirect methods were based on the interaction of DNA with other substances, such as dyes^{5,6}, drugs⁷⁻⁹ or metal complexes^{10,11}. Many organic dyes had been used in DNA analysis with spectrophotometry¹², fluorometry¹³ or light scattering technique¹⁴, such as brilliant cresyl blue¹⁵, methylene blue¹⁶ and neutral red¹⁷.

In this paper, an electroactive dye of safranin T (ST) was reported as an electrochemical probe for the determination of DNA. ST is a very commonly used cationic dye with its molecular structure shown in Fig. 1. It had been used as spectrophotometric probe for the determination of DNA¹⁸. In our selected conditions ST had a sensitive linear sweep voltammetric reductive peak at -0.43 V (vs SCE) in pH 6.0 Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution. The peak current of ST was greatly

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of safranin T (ST).

decreased by the addition of DNA with the negative shift of peak potential. The extent of the decrease of the peak current showed good linear relationship with the concentration of DNA, so a sensitive electrochemical method for the detection of DNA was proposed and further applied to the synthetic samples determination with satisfactory results. The interaction mechanism was discussed according to the spectrophotometric and electrochemical results.

Experimental

Apparatus : All the analytical determinations were performed on a JP 303 polarographic analyzer (Chengdu Apparatus Factory, China) with a traditional three-electrode system consisting of a dropping mercury working electrode (DME), a platinum wire counter electrode and

a saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE). The absorption spectra were recorded with a Cary 50 probe UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Varian, Australia). All the values of pH were measured with a pH-25 acidic meter (Shanghai Leici Instrument, China).

Fish sperm dsDNA (fsDNA) was obtained from Beijing Jingke Biochemical Reagent Company. The 1.0 mg/mL fsDNA solution was prepared by directly dissolving it in doubly distilled water, suspended until it was dissolved and stored at 4 °C. The working solution was prepared by diluting the stock solution to a certain concentration. The purity of DNA was checked by the ratio of A_{260}/A_{280} nm. A 1.0×10^{-3} mol/L safranin T (ST, Shanghai Reagent Company) solution was prepared by dissolving 0.03650 g of ST in 100 mL water. 0.2 mol/L Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution was used to control the acidity of reaction solution.

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and doubly distilled water was used throughout.

General procedure : Into a 10 mL volumetric flask, 3.0 mL of pH 6.0 B-R buffer solution, 3.0 mL of 5.0×10^{-5} mol/L ST solution and a certain amount of DNA solution was added and blended homogeneously. The solution was diluted to the scale with water and mixed thoroughly. After the reaction at 25 °C for 10 min, the linear sweep voltammograms were recorded from 0 V to -1.0 V. The peak current was recorded and the differences of peak current $\Delta I_p = (I_{p0} - I_p)$ was used for the calculation, where I_p and I_{p0} was the peak current of the system with and without the addition of DNA, respectively.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra : Fig. 2 showed the absorption spectra of ST and its mixture with different amount of

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of ST in the absence and presence of different amounts of DNA : (1) pH 6.0 B-R buffer + 5.0×10^{-5} mol/L ST; (2) (1) + 20.0 mg/mL fsDNA ; (3) (1) + 50.0 mg/mL fsDNA.

DNA. In pH 6.0 B-R buffer solution ST had a characteristic absorption peak at 510 nm, after the addition of DNA into ST solution, the hypochromism phenomenon appeared. The wavenumber of absorption peak did not shift but the decrease of absorbance value, which was the typical result of electrostatic attraction of small chromophore with DNA¹⁹.

Linear sweep voltammogram of ST with DNA : Fig. 3 showed the typical second order derivative linear sweep voltammograms of ST with DNA. There was no electrochemical response of B-R on the mercury electrode (curve 1), and ST had a sensitive linear sweep voltammetric

Fig. 3. Second order derivative linear sweep voltammograms of ST with fsDNA : (1) pH 6.0 B-R buffer; (2) (1) + 1.5×10^{-5} mol/L ST; (3) (2) + 20.0 μ g/mL fsDNA.

reductive peak at -0.43 V (vs SCE) in pH 6.0 B-R buffer, which was due to the electrode reduction of pyrazine group on the mercury electrode (curve 2). After the mixture of ST with DNA, the peak current decreased greatly with the negative shift of peak potential, which indicated that a strong binding reaction had taken place in the mixed solution. According to Bard's report, the negative shift of peak potential was the typical characteristic of electrostatic attraction of small molecule with DNA^{20,21}. So in the selected conditions ST could interact with DNA through the electrostatic attraction model to form a supramolecular complex. Based on the decrease of peak current, a sensitive DNA detection method was established in this paper.

Optimization of general procedure : The effect of pH on the interaction of ST with DNA was investigated in the pH range of 2.0~7.0 and the results were shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the difference of peak current increased with pH up to 6.0 and then decreased. So pH 6.0 buffer was recommended for the subsequent investigation.

Fig. 4. Effect of pH on the peak current : (1) 5×10^{-5} mol/L ST + 20.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ fsDNA in different pH B-R buffer solution.

The effect of ST concentration with 20.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ DNA on the peak current was investigated and the results were shown in Fig. 5. The peak current increased with the increase of ST concentration and reached maximum at 1.5×10^{-5} mol/L ST. When the concentration of ST was more than 1.5×10^{-5} mol/L, the peak current decreased, so the ST concentration was selected as 1.5×10^{-5} mol/L.

Fig. 5. Effect of ST concentration on the difference of peak current with 20.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ fsDNA in pH 6.0 B-R buffer.

The effect of reaction temperature and reaction time on the binding reaction was tested. The results showed that when the reaction temperature was in the range from 20 to 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the binding reaction reached equilibrium within 15 min and remained stable for about 3 h. So 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ was selected for reaction temperature and 15 min as reaction time.

The instrumental conditions such as the scan rate and the standing time of dropping mercury working electrode for the assay were studied. The peak current was increased with the increase of the potential scan rate in the range from 300 to 1000 mV/s and reached maximum at 1000

mV/s. So 1000 mV/s was selected as the scan rate for detection. The dropping mercury standing time for the assay was also optimized and selected as 11 s.

Effect of ionic strength : In order to investigate the effect of ionic strength on the binding reaction, different amount of 0.2 mol/L NaCl was added into the ST-DNA mixture solution and the results were shown in Fig. 6. It was found that the difference of peak current decreased with the addition of NaCl, which was attributed to the shielding effect of NaCl to the binding of ST with DNA, the cation (Na^+) competed with the DNA and the anion (Cl^-) competed with the dye, which decreased the binding ability between them. The results also indicated that the electrostatic attraction force accounted for the binding between ST and DNA.

Fig. 6. The influence of ionic strength on the peak current : (1) 5×10^{-5} mol/L ST + 20.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ fsDNA in pH 6.0 B-R buffer solution with different amount of NaCl.

Selectivity of the method : The effect of some amino acids, metal ions etc. on the determination of 20.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ DNA was tested and the results were presented in Table 1. It can be seen that most of them had little influences on the binding of ST with DNA. The method has fairly good selectivity and can be further applied to the sample determination. But the addition of ionic surfactant such as sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and biomolecules such as hemoglobin, human serum albumin (HSA) and heparin had great influences, which may be due to the formation of surfactant-DNA complex or biomolecule-ST complex.

Calibration curve for fsDNA : Under the general procedure, the calibration curve for fsDNA was established by fixing ST concentration at 1.5×10^{-5} mol/L and changing the DNA concentration. A linear relationship was found in the concentration range from 1.0 to 12.0

Table 1. Effect of coexisting substances on the determination of 20.0 µg/mL fsDNA

Coexisting substances	Concentration (µg/mL)	Relative error (%)	Coexisting substances	Concentration (mol/L)	Relative error (%)
L-Glycine	10.0	-2.30	Mg ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	4.00
L-Valine	10.0	3.90	Co ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	-3.11
L-Leucine	10.0	4.40	Ni ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.22
L-Serine	10.0	2.11	Ba ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	4.81
L-Glutamine	10.0	-3.50	Fe ³⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	-0.61
Citric acid	10.0	-4.45	Pb ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	5.55
Glucose	100.0	1.25	Cu ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	-2.15
Alcohol	1%	4.25	Hg ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	13.6
Hemoglobin	10.0	58.90	CTAB ^a	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	-69.31
HSA ^a	10.0	-44.78	SDS ^a	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	48.58
Heparin	1.00	25.30	β-CD ^a	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	-4.68

^a(Human serum albumin, HSA), (β-cyclodextrin, β-CD), (sodium dodecyl sulfate, SDS), (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, CTAB).

µg/mL with the linear regression equation as $\Delta I_p''(\text{nA}) = 58.96C (\mu\text{g/mL}) - 48.63$ ($n = 9, \gamma = 0.993$). The relative standard deviation (RSD) for 10 measurements of DNA were 4.48% with the detection limit calculated as 0.79 mg/L (3σ).

Samples determination and recovery : Four synthetic samples containing different kinds of coexisting substances were determined by this new electrochemical method. The results were shown in Table 2 and it can be seen that results obtained were satisfactory with good recovery.

Measurement of the stoichiometry of the DNA-mST complex : The binding number (m) and the equilibrium constant of the binding reaction (β_s) can be deduced with the reference to the method proposed by Li *et al.*²², which discussed the interaction of porphyrin with DNA. It was assumed that ST interacting with DNA only formed a single complex DNA-mST.

The equilibrium constant (β_s) was :

$$\beta_s = \frac{[\text{DNA} - m\text{ST}]}{[\text{DNA}][\text{ST}]^m} \quad (2)$$

and the following equation could be deduced :

$$\Delta I_{\text{max}} = kC_{\text{DNA}} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta I = k[\text{DNA} - m\text{ST}] \quad (4)$$

$$[\text{DNA}] + [\text{DNA} - m\text{ST}] = C_{\text{DNA}} \quad (5)$$

Therefore :

$$\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I = k(C_{\text{DNA}} - [\text{DNA} - m\text{ST}]) = k[\text{DNA}] \quad (6)$$

Introducing eqs. (2), (4) and (6) gave :

$$1/\Delta I = 1/\Delta I_{\text{max}} + (1/\beta_s \Delta I_{\text{max}})(1/[\text{ST}]^m) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{or } \log [\Delta I/(\Delta I_{\text{max}} - \Delta I)] = \log \beta_s + m \log [\text{ST}] \quad (8)$$

where ΔI was the peak current difference in the presence and absence of DNA and ΔI_{max} corresponded to the obtained value when the concentration of ST was much higher than that of DNA. C_{DNA} , $[\text{DNA}]$, $[\text{DNA} - m\text{ST}]$ corresponded to the total, free and bound concentration of DNA in the solution, respectively.

Table 2. Determination of DNA in synthetic samples ($n = 5$)

Sl. no.	Foreign coexisting substances	fsDNA added (µg/mL)	fsDNA found (µg/mL)	Recovery range (%)	RSD (%)
1.	Pb ²⁺ , L-arginine, L-valine, alcohol	10.00	10.12	98.9-106.3	4.07
2.	Co ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , NaCl, L-serine	10.00	10.06	99.6-101.2	1.38
3.	NaCl, Mg ²⁺ , L-glycine, L-leucine	10.00	9.93	97.8-106.7	4.20
4.	Cu ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , L-glutamine, alcohol	10.00	10.63	96.7-105.6	4.96

* Conditions : L-arginine, L-valine, L-serine, L-glycine, L-leucine, L-glutamine (10.0 µg/mL); glucose (100.0 µg/mL); Pb²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Mg²⁺, Cu²⁺, NaCl (1.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol/L); alcohol (1%).

The plot of $\log [\Delta I / (\Delta I_{\max} - \Delta I)]$ and $\log [ST]$ was calculated and it was a line with the linear regression equation as $\log [\Delta I / (\Delta I_{\max} - \Delta I)] = 7.0 + 2.00 \log [ST]$, so DNA and ST formed a single association complex. From the intercept and the slope the $m = 2.0$ and $\log \beta_s = 7.0$ were deduced, which indicated that a stable 1 : 2 complex of DNA-2ST was formed with the binding constant $\beta_s = 1.0 \times 10^7$.

Conclusion : In this paper safranin T was used as an electrochemical probe for the determination of fsDNA. In the selected conditions, ST can interact with fsDNA with electrostatic attraction model to form a biocomplex, which resulted in the decrease of peak current and negative shift of peak potential. The binding numbers and the binding constant were calculated as 2 and 1.0×10^7 , respectively. The proposed method was further applied to the synthetic samples detection with good selectivity and reproductively.

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